

METHODOLOGY OF TEACHING THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE AND LITERATURE

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Resume: The method of teaching the English language begins with teaching the language to primary school students. The first method of teaching the English language is the development of technique. The psychological and pedagogical patterns of the learning process are similar to the needs of society. At the beginning of these needs are the means of communication. The means of communication determine the ways of teaching students the English language in accordance with their linguistic characteristics. The method of teaching the English language consists of the literary parts of the language skills of students, the concepts of grammar, changes in the language system over time (assimilation) and other parts of the science of language. Methodology; Pedagogy, psychology and philosophy at the intersection of disciplines. These disciplines have a common interest.

Key words: teaching, learning, language, methodology.

Language is one of the most interesting communication tools in the hands of people. To use the language well, it is necessary to study the language features and details (Egorova, 2008). The methodology is designed to study the language concept and analytical abilities of students. The methodology is designed to test the language and analytical skills of students. (Lvov, 2007). Linguistic analysis ensures that differences between language levels are respected (Galay, 2012). The methodology also affects the level of knowledge and skills of students. The method finds the reasons for the student's successes and mistakes. There are 4 basic rules in teaching methodology. The first is "why", the second is "what to teach", the third is "how to teach", the fourth is "why not use another way".

Methodology, pedagogy and philosophy belong to the social sciences. These sciences investigate the direction of man. Methodology and these two sciences explore the language foundations, goals and objectives of language teaching. The methodology of the Russian language works with the methodology of philosophy, psychology, pedagogy and linguistics. The science of language works directly with other branches of science.

Methodology and philosophy are directly related. Language and the science of thought are directly related. Society and individual sciences are directly linked.

These results help to improve the methodology (Barabanova, 2014). According to another view, the method of teaching the Russian language includes the language skills of students, grammar, assimilation and Russian literature (Litnevskaya, 2006). Language methodology; discipline at the intersection of other disciplines, namely pedagogy, psychology and philosophy. These disciplines are of common interest (Barabanova, 2014).

In 1844, Buslaev wrote his famous work "On Teaching the Russian Language". In this work, for the first time in the history of Russian pedagogy, a system of methodology is used (Barabanova, 2014). Buslaev says that "it is necessary to distinguish between the method of teaching and the method of teaching." Buslaev study, first of all, the ability of students to correctly use information in their own speech. Buslaev compiled groups as "knowledge and skills, teachings and exercises." Second, Buslaev says that learners' learning is the role of language learning.

He divides it into two forms of learning: the student finds the truth with the help of a teacher (heuristic method) or the current knowledge of the language is acquired (dogmatic method). Usually, of these learning styles, the first method is preferred. The development of teaching methods was facilitated by Alferovan's book "Native Pity in Secondary School, Experience Method", published in 1911, and the textbooks "Russian Language", written by Shcherba in 1952. These books describe the language systems to be developed through speaking, listening, reading and writing. Thus, he bases his methodological system. Shcherba believes that the best method of teaching the Russian language is to read grammar, read literary examples and perform systematic exercises. Throughout his life, Shcherba worked on improving the quality of Soviet universities, preparing textbooks for Russian and foreign languages, and compiling school curricula. The work of Shcherba and his students was a great work on the preparation of dictionaries of the Russian language (Larin, 1977).

The research method is an important component of the general methodological - ray system - the way of interaction between the teacher and students, it is a set of methods of their joint activity. In the theory and practice of teaching the Russian language, there is no single classification according to a lower chance of learning. Some scientists use didactic classification, which is based on the characteristics of students' cognitive activity. Lerner distinguishes five methods: explanatory, content-illustrative, reproductive, problem decomposition method, partial search method (heuristic) and research. Lerner distinguishes five methods: explanatory, content-illustrative, reproductive, problem decomposition method, partial search method (heuristic) and research. In the classification of teaching methods, firstly,

the sources of knowledge are put, and secondly, the way of organizing the joint activities of local teachers and students. According to the sources of knowledge, the following methods are distinguished:

- verbal (the source is the living layers of the teacher): lecture, discussion, explanation, analysis and linguistic (observation language) analysis;
- visual: experiment, observation, practice: different types of exercises, laboratory work.

According to the method of organizing the joint activities of the teacher and students, methods are distinguished: discussion, explanation, independent work. Professor L.P. Fedorenko identifies the following teaching methods:

- Practical methods of language learning - explaining the nature of words directly, compiling oral and written messages, writing essays, drawing up plans, abstracts, notes, correcting grammatical and stylistic errors in students' speech, preparing to work with reference books.

- Methods of theoretical study of the language - communication, conversation, reading in the set of rules;

Methods of theoretical and practical study of language-exercises: analysis of language material, study of grammar-parsing, its change, presentation, grammatical design, composition, spelling and punctuation criticism, cheating, dictation, study of style - stylistic analysis, "editing".

Used literatures:

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2. Russkiy yazık. Moskva.